

Thiol Group Formation in the Vulcanisation of cis-1, 4-Polybutadiene*

DIPAK K. BASU & AJIT K. CHAUDHURI

Department of Macromolecules,

Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta-32

Received 26 September 1972

Studies are reported on the formation of thiol groups and their disappearance with time during the vulcanisation of cis-1,4-polybutadiene rubber with increasing concentrations of sulphur. The results, as in the case of natural rubber, can be explained on the assumption of three different stages depending on the sulphur concentration on the stock. The effect of different compounding ingredients on the thiol group formation has also been investigated.

Although considerable information is now available on the structural characterisation of vulcanisate networks as regards the mono-, di- and poly-sulphidic cross-linkages as well as the main chain modifications¹, nothing much is known about the formation of thiol groups and the part they play in the vulcanisation of rubber. It has been suggested by Fisher², Farmer and Shipley³, and Naylor⁴ that thiol groups are formed by the reaction of sulphur with the α -methylene groups of the rubber chain and/or addition of H₂S or H \dot{S} to the double bonds as shown below :

The thiol groups thus formed are then supposed⁵⁻⁸ to react with sulphur and/or vulcanising ingredients leading to the formation of sulphidic cross-linkages in the vulcanisate. Dogadkin and Beniska⁹ carried out some investigations on thiol group formation in the vulcanisation of sodium-butadiene rubber. The first systematic approach to evaluate the thiol groups in the vulcanisation of natural rubber (NR) on a more or less quantitative basis covering the whole range—from soft rubber to hard rubber stage—has been made by Chakravarty and co-workers¹⁰. In the present study we investigated the formation of thiol groups in the vulcanisation of cis-1,4-polybutadiene (CPBD) rubber.

EXPERIMENTAL

cis-1,4-polybutadiene rubber used in the present investigation was supplied by the Phillips Chemical Company, U.S.A., under the trade name "cis-4" having the following enchainment :

cis-1,4-configuration	...	90-93%
trans-1,4-configuration	...	3-5%
1,2-configuration	...	3-5%

*Dedicated to Professor Santi R. Palit on his sixtieth birth anniversary.

As reported by the manufacturer, the rubber contained added stabiliser 0.5%, ash 0.31%, soap 0.00% and organic acid 1.1%. The rubber was used as received without any further extraction. The compounding ingredients used were sulphur (E. Merck, sublimed), 2-mercaptobenzothiazole (R.T. Vanderbilt Co., Inc., N.Y., recrystallised), zinc oxide (B.P. Grade) and stearic acid (E. Merck, extra-pure). The vulcanising ingredients were incorporated in the rubber by means of a "Berstoff" laboratory mixing mill of size 8"×4" at about 40° with a friction ratio of 1.2, care being taken to ensure uniform dispersion of the ingredients. The compounded stock was put in a 10"×7" mould with six circular cavities of size 1.5"×0.1" in a "Wabash" hydraulic press fitted with temperature control and vulcanised under requisite pressure. The mould was preheated to almost curing temperature in the closed press for at least 20 min. The vulcanisation time was counted from the instant the press was closed and full pressure applied to the instant the pressure was released. After curing for varying periods of time, the mould was immediately put under cold water in order to arrest the reaction. The vulcanised samples thus obtained were dried and kept for 24 hr at room temperature.

The cured samples in the form of crushed powder or thin sheet, as the case may be, were subjected to cold extraction for seven days with alcohol-benzene mixture (1 : 2), the solvent being changed each day. The free sulphur and MBT were removed by this treatment. The samples were then dried in vacuum.

About 0.5 g. of the extracted and finely powdered sample was allowed to swell in a mixture of tetrahydrofuran (A.R., distilled) and glacial acetic acid (A.R.) overnight. An excess of standard silver nitrate solution (0.01*M*) was added to the swollen sample and the mixture was shaken for four hours in dark. The mixture was then transferred quantitatively to a 250 ml. beaker. About 1 g. of ammonium nitrate, dissolved in a small quantity of water, was added to the beaker. A small quantity of gelatin was then added (0.1% in the final solution) for preventing the fluctuation of the readings during titration. The mixture was then titrated amperometrically with a rotating platinum wire indicator electrode and a saturated calomel electrode against standard potassium chloride (0.02*M*) solution in order to determine the excess of silver nitrate^{6,10,11}. The reproducibility of the results was checked and found to vary within 8% in three determinations. The average of these titrations was taken.

Total and combined sulphur were determined by the standard Zinc-Nitric Acid process¹².

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CPBD rubber has been vulcanised with varying amounts of sulphur in the range 3.40–25.13% on the stock and the variation of the thiol fraction of the combined sulphur with the time of cure is shown in Fig. 1. It can be seen that for all the samples the thiol fraction passes through a maximum with reaction time. The time required to reach the maximum decreases as the proportion of sulphur in the stock is increased from 3.40–6.48% through 10.63–15.12% to 18.96–25.13%. It is also observed that the maximum in the thiol fraction goes on increasing as the concentration of sulphur in the stock is increased

from 3.40% to 6.48%, then remains more or less constant upto about 10.63% sulphur and later decreases as the proportion of sulphur in the stock is further increased.

By analogy with the case of natural rubber^{10,13} it may be assumed that in the case of CPBD also there are different stages of vulcanisation depending on the proportion of sulphur on the stock. With the lowest sulphur concentration (3.40%) the thiol fraction continues to increase upto 100 min. and then diminishes slowly upto about 300 min. attaining a more or less constant value onwards. This indicates that during the earlier part of the vulcanisation process the thiols are generated at a faster rate than they are being consumed by cross-linking or other reactions until an equilibrium is reached between the formation of thiols and their consumption. In the descending stage of the curve it is evident that the consumption of thiols becomes comparatively greater upto about 300 min beyond which the distribution of thiol groups perhaps becomes too thin to react further. The vulcanisation in the range of such low concentrations of sulphur on the stock may be considered as the "soft rubber stage" of vulcanisation corresponding to that of natural rubber.

Fig. 1. Variation of Thiol Fraction with Sulphur Concentration at 158°.

Vulcanisation with next higher concentration range (6.48–10.63%) of sulphur on the stock corresponds to that of "rotten rubber stage". Oxidative degradation reaction is known to gain prominence at this stage and the rate of depolymerisation by oxygen may in fact overtake that of the "build up" of cross-links. Apart from the contribution due to mass effect of the increased concentration of sulphur, these degradative reactions largely account for the formation of the higher proportions of thiols with these stocks (6.48–10.63% S)

Fig. 2. Variation of Thiol Sulphur with Time at 158°.

Stock Composition Rubber : Sulphur 93.52 : 6.48
 Fig. 3. Variation of Thiol Fraction with Temperature.

that at 158°. This perhaps indicates that disappearance of thiol by other reactions becomes increasingly predominant at the higher temperatures. Similar trend is observed also in the overall number of thiol sulphur with temperature (Fig. 4).

Stock Composition Rubber : Sulphur 93:52 : 6:48

Fig. 4. Variation of Thiol Sulphur with Temperature.

All these observations about the formation of thiol groups in the CPBD vulcanisate are more or less similar to those observed by Chakravarty and co-workers¹⁰ for NR, with the exception that the amount of thiols in case of CPBD is higher than in NR under otherwise identical conditions. Evidently this difference is due to the presence of the methyl groups at the double bonds in natural rubber.

Effect of Different Compounding Ingredients on the Formation of Thiol Groups : Figs. 5 and 6 show the variation of thiol groups with time of cure at 158° as the accelerator MBT and the activators ZnO and stearic acid are successively introduced in the stock. On comparison of the results with Fig. 1 it can be seen that the fraction of thiols is higher in presence of the compounding ingredients than in their absence.

Dogadkin and co-worker¹⁴ have observed that if a mixture of sulphur and MBT is heated at vulcanisation temperature, hydrogen sulphide is liberated and 2-benzothiazolyl polysulphide is formed. The rate of evolution of hydrogen sulphide increases with increasing MBT concentration at constant sulphur concentration. The authors suggested that an equilibrium reaction is involved :

Also it was observed that the rate of generation of H₂S is strongly accelerated by the addition of stearic acid to the reaction mixture.

The increased formation of thiol groups in presence of MBT may be due to this H₂S formation by reaction between MBT and sulphur and subsequent addition of H₂S to rubber. However, from activation energy considerations for H₂S formation and for MBT accelerated

Fig. 5. Effect of Different Compounding Ingredients on Variation of Thiol Fraction at 158°.

vulcanisation Dogadkin and co-worker concluded that formation of H_2S is not an important reaction in accelerated vulcanisation. They showed that MBT and sulphur are attached to rubber simultaneously and suggested that MBT and sulphur form an intermediate complex which then gives the free radicals as shown below

The authors believe that the radicals $HS_8 + \dot{S}_{8-x}$ play important roles in vulcanisation. The hydrogen polysulphide radicals HS_8 , generally speaking, can contain a variable number of sulphur atoms, and may be responsible for the increased formation of thiols in presence of MBT.

It has been observed¹⁵ that the rate of combination of sulphur in MBT accelerated CPBD vulcanisation is slowed down on addition of ZnO. Perhaps this is reflected in the smaller amounts of thiols in presence of ZnO along with MBT. As regards the presence of a minimum in the curves with ZnO and ZnO+stearic acid we are not certain whether this is a real feature of the reactions, but perhaps may indicate that beyond this stage there is further generation of thiols due to the degradative reactions.

As regards the total number of thiol groups, it can be seen from Fig. 6, that the yield of thiols with MBT accelerated stock, though initially lower than with the stock containing

Fig. 6. Effect of Different Compounding Ingredients on Variation of Thiol Sulphur with time at 158°.

added ZnO and stearic acid, becomes higher than the latter at longer times of cure. The effect of ZnO with and without stearic acid is almost the same except that towards the end the thiols are higher with ZnO in absence of stearic acid.

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